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Entomotherapy: A Concise Review

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सारांश

प्राचीन काल से ही पारंपरिक तथा आधुनिक-दोनों प्रकार की चिकित्सा प्रणालियों में कीटों तथा उनसे प्राप्त होने वाले पदार्थों का चिकित्सीय उद्देश्यों के लिए उपयोग किया जाता रहा है। विश्व में औषधीय गुणों वाली कीट प्रजातियों की संख्या हजारों में बताई जाती है। प्राकृतिक परिवेश और उसके संसाधनों के निकट संपर्क में रहने के कारण जनजातीय एवं ग्रामीण समुदायों के पास ऐसा समृद्ध पारंपरिक ज्ञान उपलब्ध है, जिसे विज्ञान और उद्योग द्वारा विभिन्न रोगों के उपचार हेतु उपयोग में लाया जा सकता है। इसके अतिरिक्त, यदि इस ज्ञान का समुचित अन्वेषण और विकास किया जाए, तो यह संबंधित समुदायों को आय का एक विश्वसनीय स्रोत भी प्रदान कर सकता है। यह समीक्षा कीटों तथा/अथवा उनके व्युत्पन्न उत्पादों के संभावित औषधीय उपयोगों पर प्रकाश डालती है।

कुंजी: एंटीबायोटिक्स, विविधता, खाद्य, कीट, मैगॉट्स

Abstract

Since ancient times, both conventional and contemporary medicine have utilised insects and the materials that can be derived from them for therapeutic purposes. There are reportedly thousands of insect species with medicinal properties in the world. Due to their intimate proximity to the natural world and its resources, tribes and rural groups possess a wealth of knowledge that might be utilised by science and industry to treat a variety of illnesses. Additionally, if explored then it will also give these associated communities a reliable source of income. This review highlights the use of insect and or their derivatives as probable medicine.

Keywords: antibiotics, diversity, edible, insects, maggots.

1. Introduction

Despite millennia of gathering and identifying the insects that inhabit our planet, it is thought that we have only discovered a portion of the total. Unplanned and unrestrained human population increase is unfortunately driving many insect species to extinction. Surprisingly, many of them are uncatalogued. The question is: why should we care about and work to conserve insect diversity? There could be various reasons for this, but one of the most important is that these species may contain information of medical use to humans (Srivastava et al., 2017). Humans have long sought drugs and supplements to treat ailments and improve their general health. Insects have long been used to treat a variety of maladies and injuries, and they have proven to be useful and yield results. However, other remedies were based on speculative assumptions and guesses, such as dung beetles for constipation, stick insects for weight loss, and hairy tarantulas for hair loss. Any creature with components that resembled human body parts was thought to be beneficial to those organs. For example, grasshopper femurs, which were thought to resemble human livers, were used to treat liver problems in indigenous Mexicans (Matt, 2014). According to several studies (Feng et al., 2009; Dossey, 2010; Ratcliffe et al., 2011), the use of insects in folk medicine has been widespread not only in China and Brazil but also in India, Mexico, Africa, and other countries. Research has been done on the chemical composition of substances found in insect

bodies that are utilised to treat a range of illnesses, such as wasp and honeybee venom (Rajkhowa et al., 2016).

2. Insects as Medicine in India

Insects have been used for thousands of years to produce valuable natural goods including silk, honey, bee wax, propolis, pollen, royal jelly, and others, but as medical resources, they have gotten very little attention (Rajkhowa et al., 2016). In India, the ancient traditional medicinal system known as Ayurveda is almost always combined with Western medicine as part of the regular medical care. While ayurvedic medicine often works, dosages might differ and often seem inefficient (Chakravorty et al., 2011).

Many illnesses, both specific and vague, are said to be treated by termites. The mound or a piece of it is frequently dug, and the termites and architectural elements are combined to produce a paste that is applied topically to the damaged areas or, less commonly, mixed with water and consumed (Srivastava et al., 2017). It was believed that this drug might treat anaemia, rheumatic ailments, and ulcers. It was also advised as a general pain reliever and health booster (Chakravorty et al., 2011). According to Chakravorty et al. (2011), many insect larvae are collected, boiled, and mashed into a paste that is administered to tropical areas and is said to boost nursing, lower fevers, and soothe digestive tracts.

3. Diversity of Insects used as/ in medicines

Almost all continents have long used insects for medical purposes, although since the discovery of antibiotics, relatively little entomological study has been conducted for

medical purposes. But because antibiotics are overused carelessly, drug-resistant bacteria strains have emerged, rendering the medications useless as a preventative measure against constantly changing infections. Drugs derived from insects are a useful tool in the fight against diseases that arise with new infections and strains of bacteria that are resistant to antibiotics (Dossey, 2010).

Table 1: table enlisting medicinal uses of insects in various diseases

Order	Scientific name (Common nae)	Disease treated	State	References
Hymenoptera	<i>Lepidotrigona arciferal</i> (Stingless bee)	Cold and cough, cancer	West Bengal	Biswa et al., 2017
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis indica</i> (Honey bee)	used as eye drops	Tamil Nadu	Solovan et al., 2004
Lepidoptera	<i>Diacrisia oblique</i> (Kambal keeda)	dog bite	Chattisgarh	Srivastava et al., 2017
Lepidoptera	<i>Helocoverpa armigera</i> (Pod borer)	fever, nervous breakdown, eosinophilia and asthma	Chattisgarh	Oudhia, 2001
Isoptera		wound healing in cattle	Orissa	Paul and Sudipta, 2011
Diptera	<i>Tipula</i> spp. (Crane fly)	healing process and to relieve body aches	Manipur	Kapesa et al., 2020
Hymenoptera	<i>Oecophylla smaragdina</i> (Red tree ant)	stomach ache and dysentery	Arunachal Pradesh	Chakravorty et al., 2011
Hemiptera	<i>Darthula hardwickii</i> (Treehopper)	body ache, jaundice	Nagaland	Mozhui et al., 2020
Hemiptera	<i>Tessarotoma javanica</i> (Litchi stink bug)	warts removal	Nagaland	Pongener et al., 2019

4. Nutritional Factors

In addition to their macronutrient value, certain insects are known to have high vitamin and mineral profiles (Ojha et al., 2021). Edible insects are great sources of protein substitutes that have a high nutritional content and may even enhance health. In insects, the dry matter protein content ranges from 25% to 75% (Barker et al., 1998; Bukkens, 1997; Cerda et al., 2001; Finke, 2002). Whether a species undergoes complete metamorphosis (holometabolous) or incomplete metamorphosis (hemimetabolous) affects the variance in amino acid patterns that it experiences over the course of its life cycles (Finke, 2002; Pieterse and Pretorius, 2014).

In dry matter, insects can have fat contents ranging from 10% to 70% (Finke, 2013; Yang et al., 2006). In addition to glycerides, other fat-soluble substances such as waxes, sterols, and fat-soluble vitamins are also included (Odincx and Finke, 2021).

In insects, carbohydrates are found in trace levels and are measured as nitrogen-free extract (Barker et al., 1998; Pennino et al., 1991).

Based on the quantity required to meet nutritional demands, minerals can be divided into two groups: micro-or trace minerals (iron, zinc, copper, manganese, iodine, and selenium) and macro-minerals (calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, sodium, potassium, and chloride). Insects frequently have low calcium levels because they lack a mineralized skeleton (Barker et al., 1998). Only a small number of studies have revealed the sodium and potassium content of insects (Reichle et al., 1969). Most bug species most likely contain these three elements in sufficient

amounts to meet the dietary needs of most animal species (Reichle et al., 1969).

5. Edible insects and bee products

Due to their high nutritional content, particularly in terms of proteins, insects are traditionally eaten as food in many parts of the world. Depending on the insect, one or more developmental stages may be consumed. It is possible to prepare insects for human food by roasting or boiling them, and sometimes adding spices. Many ethnic groups in India eat insects (Chakravorty, 2014; Hazarika et al., 2020). In India alone, some 255 kinds of insects are eaten as food by different ethnic groups. Coleopteran species make up the largest portion of these edible insect species—roughly 34%—and are followed by orthopteran species (24%), hemipteran species (17%), hymenoptera species (10%), odonatan species (8%), lepidopteran species (4%), isopteran species (2%) and, finally, ephemeropteran species (1%). The practice of entomophagy is common among the ethnic groups residing in the northeastern regions of India. This is especially true for the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, and Nagaland, and to a lesser degree, Meghalaya and Mizoram (Shantibala et al., 2014). In contrast, tribes in Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Jharkhand, and other central regions of India practise entomophagy to a lesser degree. Natural products and preparations for dietetics, nutritional supplements, and food have long been used in traditional medicine.

Bee products have a long history and are used for culinary, medicinal, and commercial purposes. The Bible, Quran, and Vedas are just a few of the holy books that mention the therapeutic qualities of bee products. Human dietary

supplements include bee bread (BB) and collected pollen (BCP) (Kieliszek et al., 2018). These days, bee products include propolis, honey, royal jelly (RJ), beeswax, and bee venom (BV).

As the modern world realises the potential of apiculture products, which are deeply embedded in ethnic communities, their use for commercial, nutritional, and therapeutic purposes is rapidly growing (Luo et al., 2021).

6. Test vehicle in laboratory (drosophila)

The common fruit fly, *Drosophila melanogaster*, has been the subject of several investigations. It was introduced as a seminal model in biology about a century ago because of its many biological, biochemical, neurological, and physiological similarities to mammals. Roughly 75% of the genes responsible for human diseases have functional homologs in *Drosophila melanogaster*, according to reports. According to some research, it is more economical and productive to use flies as models in the lab rather than vertebrates (Abolaji et al., 2013).

7. Cockroaches

There are several undiscovered medical benefits to cockroaches (Denisha et al., 2016). Having lived for millions of years on Earth, they are some of the hardiest insects. They have a maximum survival time of thirty days without food, forty-five minutes without oxygen, and thirty minutes under water. They also thrive in unhygienic environments. (Ruqaiyyah & Associates, 2022). By creating defence mechanisms against pollutants and microbes, cockroaches have adapted to their unhygienic environments and niches (Akbar et al., 2019; Ali et al., 2017). The cockroach is an omnivore. According to Lee et al. (2011), there are chemical substances entangled in cockroach heads that have the ability to eradicate Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and *Escherichia coli*. In addition to being used in traditional medicine for a variety of ailments like heart disease, asthma, digestive issues, ulcers, burns, and most importantly, cancer, cockroaches also contain antimicrobial peptides that can be used to treat and stimulate liver recovery following a hepatitis B infection (Zhao et al., 2017). Cockroaches may be a rich and diversified source of new compounds with biological activity that emerge from their tissues or gut microbiota and contribute to resilience and general health, even though there hasn't been much research on the topic.

8. Insects in robot technology

Insects and other arthropods can easily navigate complicated environments while having relatively rudimentary brain systems. Insect navigation and control are of interest to robotics. Because insects have similar difficulties with vision and navigation to that of autonomous robots, their conduct has been a major source of inspiration for the field of robotics. Researchers have begun to build robots by taking cues from insects' flight, locomotion, coordination, and other

behaviours (Lim et al., 2006). Numerous robots have been created with the intention of functioning like insects. For example, James McLurkin developed robots that acted like ants in a colony after being inspired by the ant's strength, coordination, and colonial behaviour (MIT News, 2003). The world's smallest robot was built by Robert Wood of Harvard's Microbotics lab; it measured only 2/3 of an inch with a wingspan just above an inch. IIT-Kanpur also created an AI-based insect-like robot that can fly and spy without being noticed (Times of India, 2020).

9. Maggots larvae used for wounds

An estimated 2% of people in underdeveloped nations get chronic wounds at some point in their lives. Because wound healing capacity varies with age, the prevalence rises as the population ages (Zubir et al., 2020). According to Werden et al. (2009), a chronic wound is one that has not healed over the course of three months in a timely and organised manner to restore anatomical and functional integrity. In their comprehensive review, Zubir et al. (2020) found that maggot therapy made it possible to debride non-viable tissue more quickly and successfully. In comparison to hydrogel dressings, it allowed for a faster formation of granulation tissue and a greater reduction in wound surface area. In their investigation on the efficacy of using *Lucilia sericata* larvae for chronic wound debridement, Bazalinski et al. (2019) discovered that larval therapy is a secure and reliable technique for eliminating dead tissue during wound healing. It is linked to tissue growth more quickly, disinfection, and debridement. Additionally, they state that the therapy is a somewhat cost-effective approach and may shorten the course of antibiotic therapy. Maggot therapy has been shown in a randomised clinical trial by Nezakati et al. (2020) to dramatically increase the rate of chronic wound healing.

10. Anti-cancer properties

For a long time, cancer has been the most dangerous enemy in medicine. Due to the disease's increasing global occurrence, developing an effective cancer therapy has been extremely difficult (Sinha and Choudhury, 2024). Chemotherapy and radiotherapy are the most often used treatments for cancer in humans, but surgery and immunotherapy are other prominent techniques. But these treatments come with a long list of unfavourable side effects, such as psychological problems, systemic toxicity, and the emergence of extremely drug-resistant tumour cells (Sinha and Choudhury, 2024). Drug compounds derived from insects show promise in treating cancer in a variety of in vitro and in vivo models (Dutta et al., 2019). Due to their strong biocompatibility, low biotoxicity, and anticancer and antioxidant properties, bioactive components obtained from insects have also been employed as nanoparticles, either alone or in conjunction with chemotherapeutics, to improve the administration of these medications. According to Sinha and Choudhury (2024) and Slocinska et al. (2008), there are a number of mechanisms by which the crude extracts of various edible insects and their active ingredients, including as fibroin, melittin, solenopsin, cecropin, and sericin, exert

anti-cancer and immunomodulatory effects. The lysate from *Periplaneta americana* tissue is a possible therapeutic agent against cancerous cells, according to Amin et al.'s (2022) investigation on the antibacterial and anticancer actions of the material.

11. Anti-cancer properties

Because of the substances that they contain, insects may find use in a variety of fields. However, despite their intriguing medical prospects, the study of insects as potential sources of medicine has not yet received the attention that it merits, underscoring the need for more research in this area.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this article

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